

Reaction of Diazonium Salts with Open-chain Hydroxymethyleneketones.

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It was observed by one of us (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1927, **4**, 477) that diazobenzene chloride reacts with cyclic hydroxymethyleneketones in the aldehydic phase of the latter. This was established by the fact that when diazonium chloride reacts with hydroxymethylenecyclohexanone in the presence of sodium acetate, the reaction product obtained is identical with the monophenylhydrazone of diketohexamethylene. It is evident that the formation of a monophenylhydrazone in such cases must of necessity be attended with the removal of the formyl group to give the required hydrogen for the formation of a phenylhydrazone. The reaction was accordingly represented as below :

The labile hydrogen atom which was attached to the carbon atom (*) thus migrates to a nitrogen atom, attended with a shift of double bond, causing the formation of a hydrazone. The azo derivative is,

therefore, not realised. As all these transformations are best explained by assuming the aldehyde phase, hydroxymethylenecyclohexanone need not be considered as a permanently enolised β -diketone.

Benary, Meyer and Charisius (*Ber.*, 1926, 59, 109) on the other hand, have shown that open-chain hydroxymethyleneketones react with diazobenzene chloride giving the following type of compounds, in which the formyl group remains unaffected, although the hydrazone is the final product.

To explain the elimination of the formyl group (a fact which was proved by analysis and the detection of ethyl formate in the reaction mixture) in the case of cyclic hydroxymethyleneketones as distinct from the open-chain hydroxymethylene compounds described by these authors, it was advanced by one of us that in the open-chain hydroxymethyleneketones used by Benary and his collaborators, there is a hydrogen atom in the ketone, available for the formation of phenylhydrazone, whilst in cyclic hydroxymethyleneketones, no such labile hydrogen atom is present. Hence, if the tendency to form a hydrazone is great, formyl group will have to be eliminated to supply the necessary hydrogen for the transformation of the azo derivative to hydrazone.

The present work was undertaken in-order to investigate whether it was a characteristic property of open-chain hydroxymethyleneketones to retain the formyl group, while reacting with diazonium chloride, or whether the above hypothesis holds good in all cases of reaction between diazonium chloride and hydroxymethyleneketones, cyclic or open-chain, where there was no extra hydrogen available for the formation of phenylhydrazone. With this end in view, the reaction between hydroxymethylenedesoxybenzoin (prepared by the action of ethyl formate and sodium ethoxide on desoxybenzoin in dry ethereal solution) and diazobenzene chloride was studied. According to our hypothesis, hydroxymethylenedesoxybenzoin, which is an open-chain hydroxymethyleneketone, containing no available hydrogen atom unlike Benary's compounds for the

formation of phenylhydrazone, must have its formyl group split off in the following way to give rise to monophenylhydrazone of benzil :

That the reaction product was monophenylhydrazone of benzil was proved by analysis as well as by the following facts:

(i) It was found to be identical with the monophenylhydrazone of benzil prepared by Bülow (*Annalen*, 1885, 236, 194) by warming equimolecular quantities of benzil and phenylhydrazine.

(ii) The diphenylhydrazone obtained by heating benzil and excess of phenylhydrazine was identical with the product obtained by heating our reaction product with phenylhydrazine.

The action of diazonium chloride or substituted diazonium chlorides on open-chain hydroxymethyleneketones having no available hydrogen atom for the specific reaction mentioned above, invariably gave rise to monophenylhydrazones or substituted monophenylhydrazones in the same way as in the case of cyclic hydroxymethyleneketones.

EXPERIMENTAL.

Condensation of hydroxymethylenedesoxybenzoin and diazobenzene chloride: Formation of monophenylhydrazone of benzil.—Diazotised aniline (1 mol.) was added to a solution of hydroxymethylenedesoxybenzoin (1 mol.) in aqueous alcohol containing excess of sodium acetate, cooled below 0°. A yellowish sticky mass separated which was filtered, washed with water, dried and crystallised when yellowish brown needles from dilute acetic acid were obtained, m.p. 128-29°. When crystallised from dilute alcohol, the colour becomes light yellow. It is insoluble in alkali. (Found: N, 9.5. Calc.: N, 9.34 per cent).

The filtrate was distilled on a water-bath and in the distillate, collected between 60° and 80°, a strong smell of ethyl

formate was noticed. The distillate gave a white precipitate of mercurous chloride with a solution of mercuric chloride.

The benzilmonophenylhydrazone, thus obtained, was heated with an equimolecular quantity of phenylhydrazine in the presence of a little glacial acetic acid on a water-bath for $\frac{1}{2}$ hour. The bright yellow precipitate obtained on dilution was filtered and washed with alcohol. It crystallised from hot acetic acid as bright yellow needles, m.p. 225° . It was found to be identical with benzildiphenylhydrazone, prepared otherwise. (Found: N, 14.72. Calc.: N, 14.35 per cent).

Condensation of hydroxymethylenedesoxybenzoin and diazo-p-nitrobenzene chloride: Formation of benzilmono-p-nitrophenylhydrazone.—The condensation was effected in the usual way and the product crystallised from dilute alcohol as yellowish orange needles, shrinking at 176° and melting at 180° . It is soluble in acetic acid and alcohol and is identical with benzilmono-p-nitrophenylhydrazone, prepared in other ways. (Found: N, 12.09. Calc.: N, 12.23 per cent).

Benzildi-p-nitrophenylhydrazone.—By heating the above mono-p-nitrophenylhydrazone with an equimolecular quantity of p-nitrophenylhydrazine in glacial acetic acid solution for $\frac{1}{2}$ hour on the water-bath, the di-p-nitrophenylhydrazone was prepared. On cooling and dilution with water, a reddish mass was obtained which is sparingly soluble in alcohol. This was filtered, washed and crystallised from acetic acid when deep red needles were obtained melting at 290° , identical with di-p-nitrophenylhydrazone prepared otherwise. (Found: N, 17.8. Calc.: N, 17.5 per cent).

Benzil-p-nitrophenylhydrazone-2-phenylhydrazone.—This was prepared by heating benzilmono-p-nitrophenylhydrazone with an equivalent amount of phenylhydrazine or by heating benzilmonophenylhydrazone with p-nitrophenylhydrazine. It crystallised from hot acetic acid, m.p. 255° . (Found: N, 16.0. $C_{26}H_{21}O_2N_5$ requires N, 16.09 per cent).

Condensation of hydroxymethylenephénylethylketone and diazobenzene chloride: Formation of a monophenylhydrazone of acetyl benzoyl.—The condensation product was separated in the usual way. It crystallised from dilute alcohol as pale yellow needles, m. p. $146-47^{\circ}$. It is soluble in alcohol and acetic acid. (Found: N, 12.06. $C_{15}H_4ON_2$ requires N, 11.76 per cent).

1-p-Nitrophenylhydrazone-2-phenylhydrazone of acetylbenzoyl was prepared by heating the monophenylhydrazone of acetylbenzoyl with an equivalent quantity of nitrophenylhydrazine in glacial acetic acid solution on the water-bath for $\frac{1}{2}$ hour and crystallised from hot acetic acid as deep red needles, m.p. 230° . (Found: N, 18.5. $C_{21}H_{19}O_2N_5$ requires N, 18.97 per cent).

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